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Compueducation: ICT Integration into Administrative Management of Private Secondary School Teachers and Students' Class Attendance and Classroom Attitude in Delta State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Many private secondary school administrators in Nigeria have yet to integrate information and communication technology (ICT) into their school administrative management. ICT integration into school administrative management has proven to be very effective and positively productive for managing teachers and students' class attendance and classroom attitude and it has produced enhanced learners' outcomes in advanced education systems like the United States of America, United Kingdom, Russia, China, Canada among others. In Nigeria, many private school owners have not integrated ICT into the administrative management of their schools- this has resulted in school administrators' ineffective administration and management. And this could be a reason for the alarming rate of many private school teachers' nonchalant attitude towards class attendance and teaching their subjects as well as students' poor class attendance and classroom attitude in private secondary schools in Delta State of Nigeria. This study investigated ICT integration into the administrative management of private secondary school teachers and students' class attendance and classroom attitude in Delta State of Nigeria. The population of the study consisted 250 principals in two hundred and fifty (250) Delta State's private secondary schools and from which a sample of twenty (20) respondents were purposively selected for the study. Three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The design adopted in this study was the contrast research design. A validated structured questionnaire with twelve standardised test items with a Cronbach alpha (α) reliability index of .83 was used for data collection. Data collected were analysed using Mean, standard deviation and t-test. The study revealed that both teachers and students class attendance and classroom attitude during lesson periods improved significantly with ICT integration into the administrative management of teachers and students class attendance and classroom attitude much more than when ICT was not integrated for the management of teachers and students class attendance and classroom attitude. The study measured effect sizes, eta squared (η^2) of the results to establish the practical significance of the results and found .57, .71, and .62 using Cohen's (1988, 1992) *d* criteria. The effect sizes are large which indicated that practical significance of the results is highly supported. The study concluded that ICT integration into school management has made it possible for school administrators to be more accountable and efficient in managing teachers and students' activities in the classroom. The study recommended that government should make ICT integration into the management of private secondary schools, an education policy that should be adhered to by private school owners as a way of curbing truancy, bullying, harassment and other maladaptive behaviours in Delta state's private secondary schools among others.

Keywords: Compueducation; school administrators; private secondary schools; ICT; teachers and students; administrative management, class attendance; classroom attitude.

INTRODUCTION

We are in an information age, and the nucleus of the information age is computer, and which is a product of computer science. Computer science is the fulcrum on which the information superhighway- the Internet is mainly founded. Presently, no one in any works of life can achieve any good scientific and technological innovation without inclusion of the computer as a component of such innovation, and the application of computer in administrative management is no exception. Computers are used in hospitals, industries, farms, banks, cars, aeroplanes, homes, schools, effective administrative support tool for decision-making, everywhere and in almost every aspect of life, etc. For about four decades now, computer found its way into education organisations in Nigeria. The benefits of using computers in school organisations, led to the introduction of computer science as a course of study in institutions of higher learning such as the Universities, Polytechnics, Colleges of Education, etc., across continents of the world (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

Computer science is the science which studies how the programmable electronic device (computer) is designed with its hardware and software integration, and how it is used for converting complex data into useful and meaning information needed for decision-making, and the onward transmission of information to different users through computer networks, and the development of different application softwares, for solving general-purpose problems as well as problems of specific nature, in all aspects of human specialisation. Computeducation is the study of application of computers in education- that is teaching, learning and administrative management (Omoghenemuko, 2019).

The benefits of applying computer for problem-solving in the education environment include its application for: Information and communication technologies; assessment tool for examining students' performance, school administrative management; security apparatus, online students' course registration and tuition fees' payments, instructional tool among others.

Since computer found its way into the education terrain, private schools have harnessed its use to enhance teaching and learning and administrative effectiveness more than public schools. Public schools are education outfits (tertiary, secondary, primary schools) established and managed by government. While, private school is the kind of education outfit owned or establishment and managed or undertaken by any agency or individuals other than federal or state government, for the purpose of profit-making (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

Information and communication technology (ICT) offers numerous opportunities for changes in various school-related processes like school administrative management, teaching and learning. School administrators with different management styles need modification to integrate the use of ICTs; following emergence of computer networking and Internet requiring school administrators to use computers as a management and administrative tool (Makhanu & Kamper, 2012). Schools should take advantage of these opportunities to introduce drastic changes in education infrastructure, improve skills needed by teachers and administrators to manage education institutions. ICT provides veritable tools for addressing the problems of management of a school system. It suffices to mention that, ICT helps in improving the overall effectiveness of school. ICT-driven schools or academies are suitably referred to as 'Smart schools or academies' today because of ICT-provision for administrators to enhance their administrative support for teachers' efficacy and improved students' learning outcomes (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

It is therefore evident that, for any nation to compete favourably with advanced global economies, that nation must develop the computing knowledge and skills of its citizenry. Today, ICT which is a branch of study in computer science, is the major driver of global knowledge economy and global competitiveness (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

Undoubtedly, ICT, which is the combination of computers and other data/information processing systems, telecommunication, Internet, broadcasting, multimedia and other associated technologies has promised essential change and innovation in education management within a short time and has become indispensable tool in modern school administrative management efficiency and effectiveness (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

Components of ICT

Components of ICT include: computers, television, telephones, radio equipment, CCTV cameras, multi-media, facsimile, communication networks, and know-how. These have a lot of influence in enhancing the effectiveness of instructional techniques and achievement of learning outcomes.

Division of ICT in education administration

ICT for education administrative management is divided into three categories: Monitoring instruments (TV, CCTV, Computer); Instructional (Video, DVD, and Multimedia Modules); and Dissemination (TV broadcast, Web conference, e-mail, WhatsApp and Facebook audio and video communication and text messages, Instagram, Twitter messages, etc.). But the emphasis on the choice of technology and the way it is used is partially determined by what is expected in terms of its education administrative management capability, teaching and learning, and improvement in learners' learning outcomes to achieve objectives (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

The various kinds of ICT products available and having relevance to education, such as WhatsApp video and audio conferencing, YouTube lessons, television lessons, radio broadcasts, interactive voice response system, CD-ROMs, etc; have been used in education for different purposes (Omoghenemuko, 2024; Bhattacharya & Sharma,2007).

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of ICT integration on administrative management of private secondary school teachers and students' class attendance and classroom attitude in Delta state.

Significance of the Study

This study will be beneficial to parents, students, teachers, principals and other school administrators.

To parents, the findings from the study will enable them to have knowledge about their children's classroom activities as it pertains to class attendance, behaviour in class and their level of concentration during lesson periods.

To teachers, the study will help them to make conscious efforts to teach their subjects properly and ensure that the students are motivated to learn since whatever they do in classroom during lesson hours would be seen at a glance by the school administrators.

To students, the study will help them to learn to comport themselves and be of good behaviour while in classroom/school; since their parents would easily be communicated about their classroom activities by school administrators.

To principals/other administrators, the study will help them to have complete knowledge and absolute control of whatever happens in classrooms between teachers and students during lessons, and take appropriate actions promptly.

Scope of the study

The study covers the effect of ICT integration on the administrative management of private senior secondary school teachers and students' class attendance and classroom attitude in Delta state. The study is delimited to Delta state.

Statement of the problem

The evolution of technology has given fresh impetus to the use of ICT in the management and administration of secondary schools across countries of the world and Nigeria is no exception. Although the introduction of ICT in education has gained momentum and built capacity in school administrators to adopt ICT-driven administrative management strategies for effective school administration and management. There is no evidence of the influence of ICT in public secondary schools' administrative management in Nigeria due to lack of ICT installations, and very little evidence explains the influence of ICT in private secondary schools' administrative management in Nigeria except in advanced economies like the United States of America, United Kingdom, China, Russia, Canada, where there are formidable ICT infrastructures and constant electricity power supply necessary for driving ICT-based economies. The integration of ICT into the mainstream of private school management is still very low among school administrators in Delta State' private secondary schools. Most Delta State's private secondary school have existed for about four decades, yet with administrative management styles reflecting insufficient use of ICT.

There is scanty literature on the use of ICT in the administrative management of private schools across Nigeria. However, how effective the application of ICT in the administration of private secondary schools' teachers and students' class attendance and classroom attitude in Nigeria has not been directly mentioned in any literature to the best of the researchers' knowledge. Therefore, within the context of relevance, the problem of this study is to investigate the effect of ICT integration on the administrative management of private senior secondary school teachers and students' class attendance and classroom attitude in Delta state of Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

- i. What is the improvement in teachers and students class attendance between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras to manage teachers and students' class attendance in the school?
- ii. What is the improvement in teachers' attitudes toward teaching their subjects to positively motivate students and students' concentration during lesson periods between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras; to manage teachers and students' classroom attitude in the school?
- iii. What is the improvement in the management of teachers and students by school administrators between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

- i. There is no significant improvement in teachers and students class attendance between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras to manage teachers and students class attendance in the school.

- ii. There is no significant improvement in teachers' attitudes toward teaching their subjects to positively motivate students and students' concentration during lesson periods between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras; to manage teachers and students' classroom attitude in the school.
- iii. There is no significant improvement in the management of teachers and students by school administrators between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The emergence of ICT has become a driving force for education reforms, making it possible for school managers, staff, students and parents to exchange information and ideas easily and instantly. This has been witnessed in schools having websites and confirmed by Reddi (2011) and Oyieri et al. (2015) who affirm that to assess the level of ICT use in education in Kenya, noted that schools have integrated ICT into management of finances, co-curricular activities and infrastructure and human resources management. Oguta et al. (2014) assert that ICT enhances day-to-day management of institutions and enables schools to improve in efficiency and cope with rapidly changing world in executing administrative management tasks. In support of this contention, Ngugi (2012) in an investigation into the extent of use of ICT in education management in public secondary schools in Naivasha District, Kenya noted that cost-effective application of ICT-related technology combined with flexibility in teaching and learning and administrative activities is essential in enhancing efficiency in secondary schools. ICT as management tool, has made school administrative management tasks less complex, which according to Mingaine (2013), includes coordination of teaching and learning process, along with educational programmes; financial, human resources and supporting resources, library and information science, and general administration and management. For coordination to achieve educational goals, Alexander (2012) and Oyieri et al. (2015) groups tasks as financial, administrative and instructional management. In financial management in schools. ICT has been used in budgeting, accounting and auditing, which has streamlined financial management and minimized seepage. Again, schools have used ICT in directing and controlling activities which includes staff and students' records management plus stores management and procurement implementation process. Instructional management in schools has used ICT in timetabling, examination management, academic records and teaching-learning process. The study sought to address administrative, financial and instructional management in private secondary schools in Nairobi County.

Information and communications technology (ICT) is an umbrella term that describes any communication device, encompassing: radio, television, multi-media, cellular phones, computer and network hardware and software, satellite systems and so on, as well as the various services and applications associated with them, used for the acquisition, processing and distribution of textual, vocal, pictorial, and audio-visual contents- Such as audio conferencing, video conferencing through the Internet. ICTs are often spoken of in a particular context, such as ICTs in education, health care, business, banking, libraries, etc. (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

Application of ICT in Education Administrative Management

Computer technology has also been introduced into the administrative management of colleges and universities, which not only provides a new working model for the implementation of strategic management of colleges and universities, but it also helps to improve the level of administrative management of colleges and universities, so that it can provide better services for the development of colleges and universities (Li. 2021).

Usage of ICT in management and administration involves harnessing technology for better planning, setting standards, effecting change and monitoring results of the core functions of secondary schools. O'Brien and Marakas (2011) articulate that ICT is used in maintenance of records, communication and documents management. A study carried out by Oboegbulem and Ugwu (2013) in South Eastern States, Nigeria noted that influence of ICT on management systems have changed nature of administration in secondary school by allowing information to be transferred, stored, retrieved, and processed by almost all who work, study or interact within and outside the institutions. In the study of Meryo and Boit (2012), the research revealed improved efficiency in day-to-day school operations, especially in managing information about students, teachers and other staff and resources. Based on this realization, Makewa et al. (2011) assert that integration of ICT into secondary administrative processes enhance overall students' records keeping by making them more accessible to many. However, Makhanu and Kamper (2012) further note that ICT automation of admission process from enquiry by students, applying for admissions through electronic media, registration and enrolment using computers have improved management initiatives to adequately handle both teachers, students and stakeholder-related issues. On teacher and other staff administration, Alexander (2012) asserted that ICT has enabled allocation of work, attendance, and leave management and performance appraisal, raising efficiency in task distribution, data collection and management. Oguta et al. (2014) note that ICT helps in staff management by processing of voluminous records in a quick, meticulous and impeccable manner, and

easing data retrieval. In supporting this position, Mingaine (2013) indicates that ICT can help in providing a good communication system in providing timely information internal and external users acquisition and dissemination in all institutions.

Education management involves a lot of activities like admission, record keeping, resource management, etc. ICT plays a vital role in supporting all these activities in an efficient manner. It can be used right from student administration to various resource administration in education institutions (Omoghenemuko, 2025). Omoghenemuko (2025) states that four major areas of education administrative management in which ICT can be used include:

- *Learner-related:* ICT is used for admissions; registration/enrolment; time table/class schedule; students' class attendance and classroom attitude; report card; hostel; transport; etc.
- *Teacher-related:* Using ICT for teaching-learning activities, also in other areas like maintaining records, teachers' class attendance and classroom attitude, service rules, latest decisions from central board for secondary education (CBSE), etc.
- *Library-related:* ICT tools are used for in modern Internet-driven libraries, for digital cataloging and education resource materials' online access.
- *School functioning:* Recruitment and work allotment; attendance and leave management; performance appraisal; communication through e-mails; e-circulars regarding official matters; scheduling/allocation of halls for examinations; online assessments; grading; processing and display of students' results; online fee payment, etc.

ICT in Classroom Instruction Management and Classroom Activities

Instructional management aims at improving teaching and learning processes through a deliberate emphasis on ways and means of instilling excellence in quality of instruction. Today, advances in ICT as Roberts and Sikes (2011) note, require educators to present a more efficient and modern instructional management to equip students with knowledge and skills that stimulate creativity and spur growth. This supports Meryo and Boit's (2012) assertion that effective education requires integrating ICT into management systems to foster creativity and work readiness. The instructional process is evolving rapidly with ICT integration, as noted by Makhanu and Kamper (2012). Traditional tools like blackboards and textbooks are giving way to digital alternatives like smart boards, flash drives, and data projectors, making learning more engaging. ICT also reduces administrative burdens, such as record-keeping and grading. According to Makewa et al. (2011), ICT can be used in formulation and implementation of learning modules. Besides, ICT enhances instructional management by facilitating learning scheme development, staff coordination, and teaching-learning processes. By streamlining instructional management, ICT helps achieve educational goals (Zuppo, 2012). Effective ICT integration guides teachers and students toward desirable behaviors, bridging gaps in the educational process.

With ICT scheduling of classes and other resources, handling internal and external examination activities can be achieved with increased efficiency in secondary schools.

Conceptualization of School Administration and Administrators

School administration encompasses managing various aspects of a school, including creating a safe learning environment and overseeing the budget. Secondary school administrators, such as principals, assistant principals, and support staff, work together to ensure the school runs smoothly. Their roles vary depending on the level of education, with nursery, primary, and secondary schools typically having different administrative structures than colleges of education, polytechnics and universities, etc. In higher education, administration duties are often divided into areas like admissions, student affairs, and academic planning, heading departments. Each area has its own set of responsibilities, such as admissions officers determining which students to accept and student affairs administrators advising students and planning viable academic programmes with the academic calendar (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

Higher or tertiary education administration- school administration at the post-secondary, is somewhat more intricate because universities, polytechnics and colleges of education, being larger are differently and better organized than primary and secondary schools. Tertiary education often decomposes school administration tasks into: Registrar's office, admissions office, school library, students' affairs, academic planning administrator overseen by provost or dean. For instance, post-secondary education Servicom's administrator oversees which lecturers attended lecture and which did not attend, while admissions officer determines students to admit into departments or not, while dean of students' affairs/students' administrator advises students and plan programmes for students once they arrive school (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

To become a school administrator, one typically needs relevant experience and education. For example, secondary school principals usually require a master degree in educational leadership and a state license. In higher education, administrators often need a master degree, and some positions may require a doctoral degree or significant administrative experience

School administrator’s job description. School administrator plays a crucial role in providing a high-quality learning environment and educational experience for students. Their responsibilities may include:

- Overseeing teachers and support staff;
- Planning academic calendars;
- Disciplining students;
- Curriculum standards implementation;
- Class schedules creation;
- Setting security procedures and rules;
- Measuring students’ academic achievement;
- School budget handling;
- Communicating with parents.

Figure 1

ICT integration into school administrative management diagram

Figure 2

Conceptual framework

Theoretical Framework

The theory that can properly explain and help readers to comprehend, and predict the effect of ICT integration on the management of private senior secondary school teachers and students' class attendance and classroom attitude, is the scientific management theory.

Friederic Taylor's scientific management theory advocated for definition of daily tasks and use of appropriate tools to perform them (Oyieri et al., 2015), and matching an employee to perform a task that the employee was trained to do in regard to the employee's skill level and then training the employee to perform that job in a specific way. Adu and Adu (2013) state that: ICT is used in information management to enable effective administrative and instructional tasks in a school; ICT enables information about school policies and measures to easily be accessed for implementation of school programmes; ICT as a tool, provides students and teachers with information on their availability in class and conditions of textbooks, visual aids, science laboratory equipment for effective teaching and learning process in schools.

The significance of the scientific management theory to this study is that, it explains how school administrator can use ICT platform for the effective management of teachers, students, other staff, school facilities, and for effective teaching and learning; to achieve education goals and ultimately enhance the learners' learning outcomes.

METHOD

Research Design

The design adopted in the study was the ex-post facto or causal comparative design (also known as contrast design). Robinson in Fagbohunge (2009) states that the causal comparative or contrast design is used primarily in the analysis of historical data- The number of cases of which are too small to permit meaningful statistical manipulation

Population of the Study

The population for this study consisted of all Delta State's private secondary schools that have integrated ICT in the administrative management of their schools.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for this study was twenty (20) respondents (that is, 20 administrators). The sample was drawn using purposive sampling technique to select twenty schools (20) that have integrated ICT in the administrative management of their schools out of over three hundred (300) Delta State's private secondary schools.

Instrumentation

The instrument used for data collection is the researchers-constructed questionnaire titled: 'Effect of ICT Integration on the Management of Private Secondary School Teachers and Students' Class Attendance and Classroom Attitude (EIIMPSSTSCACA)' questionnaire. The instrument was divided into four sections: A, B, C and D. Section A was designed to retrieve information from the respondents on personal data, section B contained questions on teachers and students class attendance. Section C contained items structured to find out teachers and students classroom attitude. Section D contained items to determine administrators' level of management of teachers and students in classroom in private secondary schools. The response format of section B, C, and D of the instrument, used the four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA) 4; Agree (A) 3; Strongly Disagree (SD) 2; and Disagree (D) 1.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument ‘effect of ICT Integration on the Management of Private Secondary School Teachers and Students’ Class Attendance and Classroom Attitude (EIIMPSSTSCACA)’ questionnaire was face and content validated by giving copies of the questionnaires to experts in educational research methods and statistics, and test measurement and evaluation; and after proper scrutiny, it was certified suitable for the study.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was determined by Cronbach alpha (α) reliability method using the IBM SPSS version 27 for its computation. The reliability of the research instrument yielded Cronbach’s alpha (α) reliability index of 0.83 based on the twelve (12) standardised items of the instrument. Thus, confirming the instrument’s reliability and suitability for the study.

Method of Data Collection

The twenty (20) copies of the ‘ICT Integration on the Management of Private Senior Secondary School Teachers and Students’ Class Attendance and Classroom Attitude (IMPOSSTSCACA)’ questionnaire administered on the respondents (20 principals or administrators) by the researchers, were used for the study. Instructions guiding the filling of the questionnaire was clearly explained to the respondents. The filled copies were retrieved for analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

The data for this study were analysed using (Mean and standard deviation) to answer the research questions. The criterion Mean was found based on the weighted 4- point Likert scale of: Strongly Agree (SA)- 4; Agree (A)- 3; Disagree (D)- 2; and Strongly Disagree (SD)- 1. That is, $(4+3+2+1)/4 = 10/4 = 2.5$. The t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at .05 level of statistical significance.

If the computed Mean was greater than the criterion Mean of 2.5, then the researcher accepted that research question as a good item for the study, but if the computed Mean was lesser than the criterion Mean of 2.5, then the researchers rejected that research question as unnecessary item for the study.

For the hypotheses testing, if P-value was lesser than .05 ($p < .05$) then the null hypothesis was accepted, but if P-value was greater than .05 ($p > .05$) then the null hypothesis was rejected.

The study also reported effect sizes, eta squared (η^2) of the results using Cohen’s (1988, 1992) *d* criteria for effect size measurement (Table 1) to establish the practical significance of the results of the study.

Table 1. Cohen’s *d* Benchmark for effect size measurement for independent sample t-tests

Statistic	Value	Interpretation
Cohen’s <i>d</i> for independent t-tests	0.20 – 0.49	Small effect size. Noticeably smaller than medium but not so small as to be trivial.
	0.50 – 0.79	Medium effect size. An effect likely to be visible to the naked eye of a careful observer.
	0.80 -1.00	Large effect size. The same distance above medium as small below it (p.156).

Source: Igwebuike, T. B. (2022). Educational research methods and statistics: An introduction.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the improvement in teachers and students class attendance between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras to manage teachers and students class attendance in the school?*

Table 2. Means and standard deviations of items on teachers and students class attendance between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras to manage teachers and students class attendance in the school

S/N	Items on Teachers and Students Class Attendance	n	ICT-based Class Attendance Management				Criterion Mean	n	No use of ICT in Class Attendance Management		
			Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Remark	Mean (\bar{x})			SD	Remark	
1.	Teachers do not go late to school and they attend classes to teach their subjects regularly.	20	3.75	.86	Accepted	2.5	20	1.13	.20	Rejected	
2.	Students do not go late to school and they attend classes regularly	20	3.25	.78	Accepted	2.5	20	1.88	.22	Rejected	
Grand Mean			3.5	.84				1.51	.21		

Results in Table 2 revealed that all two items on teachers and students’ class attendance related to ICT-based class attendance management were rated by the respondents with the Mean of 3.75 and 3.25 respectively and a grand Mean of 3.50, which were greater than the criterion Mean score of 2.50. While for all two items on teachers and students’ class attendance related to no use of ICT for class attendance management, were rated by the respondents with the mean of 1.13 and 1.88 respectively and a grand mean of 1.51, which were lesser than the criterion Mean of 2.50. Therefore, the researchers conclude that, there is a significant improvement in teachers and students class attendance between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras; to manage teachers and students class attendance in the school; in favour of when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms for the management of teachers and students class attendance in the school.

Research Question 2: *What is the improvement in teachers’ attitudes toward teaching their subjects to positively motivate students and students’ concentration during lesson periods between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras; to manage teachers and students’ classroom attitude in the school?*

Table 3. Means and standard deviations of items on improvement on teachers' attitudes toward teaching their subjects to positively motivate students and students' concentration during lesson periods between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras; to manage teachers and students' classroom attitude in the school

S// N	Item on Teachers and Students Classroom Attitude	n	ICT-based Classroom Attitude Management			Criterion Mean	No use of ICT in Classroom Attitude Management			
			Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Remark		n	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Remark
3.	Teachers attitude towards students during lesson periods is positive and motivational.	20	3.5	1.42	Accepted	2.5	20	2	0	Rejected
4.	Students attitude towards teachers and fellow students during lesson periods is positive.	20	3	0	Accepted	2.5	20	1.63	.38	Rejected
5.	Teachers are motivated to prepare lesson appropriately and ensure that they teach to motivate the students to learn knowing that administrator is on a watch.	20	3.75	1.26	Accepted	2.5	20	1.63	0.28	Rejected
6.	There is great improvement in students' concentration during lesson periods.	20	3.25	1.16	Accepted	2.5	20	2	0	Rejected
7.	Issues and reports of missing notebooks, mobile phones, textbooks and pens ended abruptly.	20	3	0	Accepted	2.5	20	2	0	Rejected
8.	Teachers and Students are aware that administrator monitors every activity in classrooms during lesson and will give reports of their behaviours to their parents or guardian.	20	3.25	1.38	Accepted	2.5	20	1.25	0.30	Rejected
Grand Mean			3.29	0.87				1.75	0.16	

Result in Table 3 revealed that all the six items on teachers and students' classroom attitude related to ICT-Based teachers and students classroom attitude management, were rated by the respondents with the mean of 3.50, 3.00., 3.75, 3.25, 3.00, and 3.25 respectively and a grand Mean of 3.29, which were greater than the criterion Mean of 2.50. While for all the six items on teachers and students' classroom attitude related to ICT-Based teachers and students classroom attitude management, were rated by the respondents with the Mean of 2.00, 1.63, 1.63, 2.00, 2.00 and 1.25 respectively and a grand mean of 1.75, which were lesser than the criterion Mean Of 2.50. The researchers

therefore conclude that, there is a significant improvement in teachers' attitudes toward teaching their subjects and it positively motivate students and students' concentration during lesson periods between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras; to manage teachers and students' classroom attitude in the school, in favour of when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms for the management of teachers and students' attitude in the school.

Research Question 3: *What is the improvement in the management of teachers and students by school administrator between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom?*

Table 4. Means and standard deviation of items on improvement in the management of teachers and students by school Administrator between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom

S/ N	Items on Administrator's Classroom Management	n	ICT Integration-enabled Classroom Management				Criterion Mean	No use of ICT for Classroom Management			
			Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Remark	n		Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Remark	
9	Administrator is able to know Teachers and students who do not attend classes on a daily basis	20	4	0	Accepted	2.5	20	2	0	Rejected	
10	Administrator is able to check teachers and students' classroom activities regularly	20	3.5	1.73	Accepted	2.5	20	2.25	.52	Rejected	
11	Administrator is able to give progress reports of students' behaviour in school to parents with video clips	20	2	1.27	Accepted	2.5	20	2	0	Rejected	
12	Administrator is able to manage staff and students effectively	20	4	0	Accepted	2.5	20	2	0	Rejected	
Grand Mean			3.38	.75			2.06	.13			

Results in Table 4, indicated that all the four items on the management of teachers and students by school administrator between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom, were rated by the respondents with the mean of 4.00, 3.50, 2.00 and 4.00 respectively and a grand Mean of 3.38, which were greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. While for all the four items on the management of teachers and students by school administrator between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom, were rated by the respondents with the Mean of 2.00, 2.25, 2.00 and 2.00 respectively and a grand Mean of 2.06, which were lesser than the criterion Mean score of 2.50. The research therefore, concludes that, there is a significant improvement in the management of teachers and students by school Administrator between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom, in favour of when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms for the management of teachers and students in school.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant improvement in teachers and students class attendance between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras to manage teachers and students class attendance in the school.

Table 5. T-test of group means of management of teachers and students class attendance

Group Class Attendance Management	n	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Standard Error	t	P-value	Effect Size Eta squared (η^2)
ICT-Assisted Teachers'/Students' Class Attendance Management	20	3.50	.84		12.23	.000*	.57
Teachers'/Students Class Attendance Management without ICT		1.51	.21	.12			

* Significant at the .000 level (2-tailed)

Results in Table 5 indicated that ICT-assisted teachers'/students' class attendance management group with a Mean of 3.50 is significantly better than teachers'/students' class attendance management group without ICT assistance with a Mean of 1.51 [$t_{(38)} = 12.23, p=.000 < .05$]. The null hypothesis was rejected, which indicated that there is a significant improvement in the management of teachers and students class attendance by school Administrator between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classrooms, in favour of ICT-assisted teachers'/students' class attendance management. The effect size, eta squared (η^2) value of .57 using Cohen's (1988, 1992) *d* criteria, is medium (See Table 1), indicating that practical significance of the results is highly supported.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant improvement in teachers' attitude towards teaching their subjects to positively motivate students and students' concentration during lesson periods between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras; to manage teachers and students' classroom attitude in the school.

Table 6 T-test of group means of management of teachers and students classroom attitude

Group Classroom Attitude Management	n	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Standard Error	t	P-value	Effect Size Eta squared (η^2)
ICT-Assisted Teachers'/Students' Classroom Attitude Management	20	3.29	.87		13.04	.02*	.71
Teachers'/Students' Classroom Attitude Management without ICT		1.75	.16	.14			

* Significant at the .02 level (2-tailed)

The results in Table 6 indicated that ICT-assisted teachers'/students' classroom attitude management group with a mean of 3.29 is significantly better than teachers'/students' classroom attitude management group without ICT assistance with a mean of 1.75 [$t_{(38)} = 13.04, p=.02 < .05$]. The null hypothesis was rejected, which indicates that there is a significant improvement in the management of teachers and students by school administrator between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classrooms, in favour of ICT-assisted teachers'/students' classroom attitude management. The effect size, eta squared (η^2) value of .71 using Cohen's (1988, 1992) *d* criterion, is medium (See Table 1), indicating that practical significance of the results is highly supported.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant improvement in the management of teachers and students by school Administrator between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom

Table 7

T-test of group means of administrator's management of teachers and students

Teachers'/Students' Management	n	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Standard Error	t	P-value	Effect Size Eta squared (η^2)
ICT-Assisted Teachers'/Students' Management	20	3.38	.75		13.61	.000*	.62
Teachers'/Students' Management without ICT-Assistance	20	2.06	.13	.15			

* Significant at the .000 level (2-tailed)

The results in Table 7 indicated that ICT-assisted teachers'/students' management group with a mean of 3.38 is significantly better than teachers'/students' management group without ICT assistance with a Mean of 2.06 [$t_{(38)} = 13.61, p=.000 < .05$]. The null hypothesis was rejected, which indicated that there is a significant improvement in the management of teachers and students by school Administrator between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras, in favour of ICT-assisted teachers'/students' management. The effect size, eta squared (η^2) value of .62 using Cohen's (1988, 1992) *d* criterion, is medium (See Table 1), indicating that practical significance of the results is highly supported.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This study examined the influence of ICT integration on the management of private senior secondary school I teachers and students' class attendance and classroom attitude. The results provided evidence that ICT integration in school management improved both teachers and students class attendance and classroom attitude significantly. The results of this study agree with that obtained by Krishnaveni and Meenakumari (2010); Oyieri et al. (2015); and Oguta et al. (2014), which indicate that the integration of ICT in schools has made it possible for educational managers to be more accountable and efficient in managing teachers and students in classroom.

Results in Table 2, indicated that all two items on teachers and students class attendance related to ICT-based class attendance management were rated by the respondents significantly much higher than all two items on teachers and students class attendance related to no use of ICT for class attendance management. And results in Table 3, indicated that all six items on teachers and students' classroom attitude related to ICT-based teachers and students classroom attitude management were rated by the respondents significantly much higher than all six items on teachers and students' classroom attitude related to no use of ICT for teachers and students' classroom attitude management. The results of this study are corroborated by Meryo and Boit (2012) whose study revealed improved efficiency in day-to-day school operations, especially in managing information about students, teachers and other staff and resources. The results of the study are also supported by Makewa et al. (2011) who note that ICT can now be used not only in formulation and implementation of schemes of work, but also in coordinating staff for effective teaching and learning processes.

Results in Table 4, indicated a significant improvement in all the four items on the management of teachers and students by school administrator between when CCTV cameras were installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom, in favour of ICT integration for the effective management of teachers and students by school administrators. And the results in Table 5 indicated that teachers and students' class attendance management improved significantly with the integration of ICT more than teachers and students' class attendance management without ICT integration for class attendance management.

The results in Table 6 indicated that teachers and students' classroom attitude improved significantly with the integration of ICT in the mainstream of classroom management more than teachers and students' classroom attitude management without ICT integration for classroom management. And the results in Table 7 indicated that the general management of teachers and students in class after the integration of ICT was significantly more effective

than management of teachers and students before the integration of ICT for school management. The results of the study revealed that ICT as a management tool, definitely made school management tasks less complex, and this was corroborated by Oyieri et al. (2015) and Mingaine (2013) who stated that ICT integration in school management helps in proper coordination of teaching and learning process and school's general administration and management. Again, the effect sizes, eta squared (η^2) values of .57, .71, and .62 of the results of this study using Cohen's (1988, 1992) *d* criteria, are large (See Tables 1, 5, 6, and 7), which indicated that practical significance of the results is strongly or highly supported.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained in this study support the conclusion that the integration of ICT for the management of private secondary school teachers and students' class attendance and classroom attitude, significantly led to a more effective management of teachers and students' class attendance and classroom attitude than when ICT was not integrated in the management of private secondary school teachers and students' class attendance and classroom attitude among private secondary school in Delta State of Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The research made the following recommendations.

1. School administrators should ensure ICT is properly integrated into the mainstream of their school administrative management process, by mounting closed circuit television (CCTV) cameras in classrooms. This would certainly help school administrators to properly monitor teachers and students class attendance and their classroom activities at a glance; without relying on gossips.
2. Government should make a policy that would compulsorily demand ICT integration a necessary precondition for private secondary schools to operate in Delta state. This would help school administrators in secondary schools to curb truancy and other maladaptive behaviours of teachers and students, and non-teaching staff alike.

REFERENCES

- Adu, E. O. & Adu, E. O. (2013). The use and management of ICT in schools: Strategies for school leaders. *European Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology (EJCSIT)*, 1(2), 10-16.
- Fagbohunbe, O. B. (2009). The basics of research methodology. Kotleb publisher, Shomolu, Lagos, Nigeria. ISBN 978-232-261-4.
- Gupta, M., Kumar, P. P., & Bhattacharya, J. (2004). Government Online-Opportunities and Challenges. Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd., New Delhi.
- Igwebuike, T. B. (in prints). Educational research methods and statistics: An introduction.
- Krishnaveni, R. & Meenakumari, J. (2010). Usage of ICT for Information Administration in Higher education Institutions: A study". *International Journal of Environmental Science and Development*, 1(3), 282-286. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7763/IJESD.2010.V1.55>.
- Li, S. (2021). Application of Computer Technology in Administrative Management". *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1769, 5th International Conference on Computer Science and Information Engineering (ICCSIE 2020) 23-25, Dalian, China, 2021).
- Makewa, L., Role, E., & Nyamboga, R. (2011). Teacher evaluation of the principal's leadership characteristics related to computer studies implementation in Rongo District, Kenya". *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology (IJCDICT)*, 7(2), 5-14.
- Makhanu, E. & Kamper, G. (2012). The relationship between administrators' access to information and communication technology (ICT) and School Performance in Kenya. University of South Africa, Pretoria 003". <http://www.heraldjournals.org/hjegy/archive.htm>.
- Meryo, D. K. & Boit, J. M. (2012). The challenges of using information communication technology in school administration in Kenya". Moi University.
- Mingaine, L. (2012). Skill challenges in adoption and use of ICT in public secondary schools in Kenya. <http://www.ijssnet.com/Journals/vol.3-No-13-July-2013/8.pdf>.
- Ngugi, P. (2012). An investigation into the extent of use of ICT in education management in public secondary schools in Naivasha District, K. U.", 2012.

- Oguta, J. O. Egessa, R. K. W., & Musiega, D. (2014). Effects of ICT application on strategic educational quality standards management in Bungoma county, Kenya". *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 3(5), 11-17.
- Omoghenemuko, G. I. & Okurumeh, G. O. (2018). Information and communication technology (ICT): A tool for effective vocational and technical education in Nigeria". *Journal of Vocational and Technical Education (JOVTE). Issues of Researches in Vocational and Technical Education*, 3(1), 42-55., 2018.
- Omoghenemuko, I. G. (2025). Information and communication technology (ICT) in education: A global perspective. COEWA Publishers, Nigeria. ISBN 978-33794-6-7
- Omoghenemuko, G. I. (2024). Effects of transformational leadership in the classroom on NCE educatees' cognitive and affective achievement and self-efficacy beliefs in computer science. A Master Dissertation submitted to the Postgraduate School in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Master in Education (M.Ed) (Educational Administration) in the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, PortHarcourt, Nigeria., 2024.
- Omoghenemuko, G. I. (2019). Information and communication technology (ICT): A tool for modern day slavery. A lecture note. Unpublished., 2019.
- Oyieri, C. R. Odundo, P. A., Ganira, K. L.& Wangui, K. R. (2015). Effects of ICT integration in management of private secondary schools in Nairobi County, Kenya: Policy options and practices. *World Journal of Education*, 5(6). Sciedu Press 14, ISSN 1925-0746 E-ISSN 1925-0754. <http://wje.sciedupress.com>, 2015.
- Reddi, U. V. (2011). Role of ICTs in education and development: Potential, pitfalls and challenges. <http://www.unesco.org/education/aladin/paldin/pdf/cpourseol/unit-13pdf.>, 2011.